

Soft Measures Speeding up the Change – Showcases from the City of Turku, Finland

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Abstract

Mobility Management is a concept to promote sustainable transport and manage the demand for car use by changing attitudes and behaviour through so called “soft” measures (for example, information and service provision, communication or coordination). Mobility management measures do not generally require large financial investments, tend to have a high benefit-cost ratio, and are generally well accepted by citizens. They are often used as complementary activities to other “harder” measures. The City of Turku piloted three soft measures: a digital service map and two nudges. A wide team was included in both measures right from the initial planning phase. Cities can bring together relevant actors ranging from evaluators to service design to complement the work done in topic related departments. Collaboration between different actors ensures that planned actions are not only functionally executed but also designed for diverse target groups and properly evaluated. Wide enough cooperation paves the way for future scaling of successful activities with a deeper impact on travel behaviour.

Keywords: Soft measures, Nudge, Digital

1 Soft measures

1.1 Mobility management

Mobility Management is a concept to promote sustainable transport and manage the demand for car use by changing travellers’ attitudes and behaviour through so called “soft” measures. These include a range of activities related to information provision and communication, service provision and coordination of different actors. Many times, mobility management measures in comparison to “hard” measures do not necessarily require large financial investments and may have a high benefit-cost ratio [1]. In addition, citizen acceptance of “soft” measures tends to be higher than with measures targeting, for example, infrastructure [2]. In general, the effectiveness of both “soft” and “hard” measures seems to depend on various socio-psychological factors, the type of information used in communicating of the measures as well as the physical urban context within which the measure is carried out [3].

An important part of the soft measures are specific targets and evaluation actions that aim to verify the impact of the action. Research suggests an average 10% decrease in car use when using soft measures [4,5] and a reasonable cost-benefit ratio. [6] However, due to the complexity of travel behaviour, it may be difficult to verify the actual impact a specific 'soft' measure has on travel behaviour. A review of 141 soft measure related interventions [4], indicates that without proper evaluation, careful study design or precise information on the study design the causality between the intervention and the attributed behaviour change may be difficult to demonstrate. Therefore, careful planning of soft measures is needed to provide a cost-effective alternative or a complementary activity to other actions. In addition, if digital channels of information and communication are used these should be planned together with other intended measures. Digital tools are in many cases developed and evaluated in isolation from the overall mobility management actions. This may lead to isolated platforms, apps and user interfaces and can have a negative impact on the impact of the soft measures.

Very often cities lack to perform valuable evaluation actions in connection with measures. This is in many cases due to the lack of ownership, strategic and systematic approach in actions. There is a clear need in cities to strengthen the role of the soft measures in the actions towards sustainable mobility. It is not enough to create high quality infrastructure and services without understanding their full potential and not nudging citizens towards the behaviour changes needed.

1.2 Circumstances for change

The city of Turku has passed 200 000 inhabitants in August 2023 being the sixth largest city in Finland [7]. The functional urban area of the Turku has more than 340 000 inhabitants and it's the third largest in Finland [8]. The city of Turku is the oldest city in Finland turning 800 years in 2029. Turku aims to become carbon neutral by the anniversary and increase the share of sustainable transport over 66% by year 2030 [9]. Meeting these goals require big emission cuts in terms of traffic and large behavioural changes.

An important part of this is the large transport reform projects, increasing the amount of bike lanes and investing in walking conditions, as well as tightening parking regulations. These hard measures require a great political will to be implemented and they are not very agile and fast, for example, the planning of traffic reform projects may take years. Fortunately, there are also various so-called "soft measures" to speed up the change in traffic towards a more sustainable direction and to influence on people's behavior. These soft measures are vital parts of the Sustainable Urban Mobility Plan of the Functional Urban Area of the Turku region.

2 Measures piloted

2.1 Mobility map

In the city of Turku, various soft measures have been developed and tested in the EU-funded Scale-up project [10]. In 2022, Turku's mobility service map was launched, from which it is possible to encourage, visualize and monitor various mobility data in the city of Turku and in the Turku region. Through the mobility service map, for example, you can check whether the route of your way to and from work has been plowed from the snow, which makes it more convenient to cycle in the winter, as it is easier to predict the conditions of the commute route. A lot of focus has been on showcasing bike services, walking routes and real time parking situations. All the shared mobility offers can be found from the map and be combined with service and accessibility of different locations. This acts as incentives for example for tourism locations and inter-regional travel.

The mobility map is currently the only map that can showcase real time data from variety of sources and offer the content in Swedish and English. The number of users visiting the map has increased every time the mobility map has been showcased in local media. The biggest number of users so far is from February 2023 after media announcement and article on the local newspaper Turun Sanomat [11].

The mobility map is created by open-source code, so it is freely available for others to scale up [12]. Through the embedding tool, the mobility map can be added to any website and this enlarges the usability of the map considerably as all the actors interested can use it freely. One of the most valued features of the mobility map is that all the information is on one place and mobility is not anymore separated from the services.

The mobility map has been created using service design process in several stages of the process. This has led to an increased understanding of the needs of different user groups and how those can be met through mobility map. Evaluating a digital tool is very often based on usage and the number of data sets. One of the most interesting approach for the real impact is, how different actors have used it for their needs and also integrated in their communications campaigns and guidance elements. This often means that the resources are saved in other divisions of the city and within stakeholder organizations as the information needed is already provided for them. This can be considered as the repel effect of creating a common digital platform. At this stage, there is still a need to find a way to create a traceable evaluation for it.

2.2 Nudges

In addition to the mobility service map, mobility nudges are playing an important role, as their purpose is to influence people to change their behaviour in terms of mobility towards the desired direction. Originally developed by Thaler and Sunstein [13], nudging has become a common means to encourage, for example lifestyle changes [14], modal shift [15,16], or energy saving [17,18]. There are many ways to categorize nudges, but one simple way is to divide nudges into two types: 'pro-social' and 'pro-self' [19]. 'Pro-self' nudges encourage behaviour that is beneficial for an individual, whereas 'pro-social' nudges aim to help the target group choose behaviours that are

beneficial for society. Nudging should not force the target to behave in a certain way but should always make it possible to opt out.

There are numerous examples of successful nudges around the world, and at best they are easy and inexpensive to implement. During the years 2023 and 2024, ten different nudges will be implemented in Turku, focusing on different areas of mobility and traffic. The purpose of these nudges is to support both the transition from own car to sustainable modes of transport and to improve the conditions and usability of sustainable modes of transport, as well as increase the citizen engagement. The nudges will also be aimed at different target groups, such as workers, cyclists and students.

In the winter of 2023, in Turku, the first nudge was carried out, which was targeted at schools and kindergartens. The purpose of the nudge was to increase active school trips of children by means of simple gamification. The nudge was based on a visually motivating sticker campaign and very cost-effective study design. Alongside the polar bear sticker campaign, a communication campaign was carried out, providing schools, daycares, and parents with practical tips for everyday mobility. A survey for the parents was conducted after the pilot campaign. Despite its low response rate, the survey provided valuable information on how to improve the nudge. Key findings from this experiment highlighted the need for careful pre-planning, incentivizing survey responses, and the importance of age group-based targeting.

Second nudge was launched in October 2023. The regional public transportation card was introduced to citizens as part of the public library system in three different libraries. Individual library users can borrow the public transport card once for two weeks. The aim is to test what kind of effect this can have on changing the perception of using the public transportation and into becoming a regular user. If the nudge is successful, the offer can be enlarged to all the municipalities within the public transportation network.

The intensive development of the nudges has been carried out in wide cooperation with stakeholders in order to create win-win synergies. This has led to a further understanding that there is a need to differentiate that different stages. In some of the nudges a service design of the product needs to be carried out before any intervention can happen, whereas in some nudges it is a matter of targeted marketing of alternative options. Both of these are directly linked to the evaluation of the effectiveness of the nudge and how this can be carried out.

3 Key Findings of soft measures

At this stage of the process, it can be already showcased that a shared common vision of the future is needed as a base for developing effective soft measures. The role of the city in this is crucial as the city acts as a gluer between the different actors and as an enabler creating conditions for all the actors to flourish. Cooperation with different research institutions is one of the win-win situation, as the evaluation actions of the different soft measures is a must and this knowhow is not yet adequately existing nor

resourced in cities. Without the evaluation, the measures could not be adequately scaled up. This is well showcased in the case of the mobility map and also in nudges.

The development of a digital mobility map has showcased that integrating data from variety of sources in a user-friendly format creates synergies for many actors. Open data and open source code create a base for resource efficiency and open up the work for others to scale up. The development of the mobility map in design sprints is efficient and enables launching of the new features in stages. This then speeds up the development and increases the interest of the stakeholders creating a dynamic process. The focus on accessibility of the different elements adds up to the process and increases the dialogue.

Lessons learnt from developing and carrying out nudges have pinpointed that tailored target group orientation with suitable evaluation actions is crucial. Carefully planned evaluation together with the overall design may increase the impact of a nudge and may help in avoiding some of the potential pitfalls at the execution phase. Successful nudging requires tight cooperation with different actors. In some cases, the nudging needs a service design phase with different service providers before the actual nudge can take place.

Key ingredients

Digital:

- Integrating data in user-friendly format.
- Open data and open source code
- Design sprints with new launches
- Accessibility elements

Nudges:

- Tailored target group orientation needed
- Evaluation planned before action
- Tight cooperation between different actors
- Integration into service design processes

At the next stage the two elements – the mobility map and nudges will be synchronized and it is expected that this will increase the speeding effect of the soft measures to the next level. This all is expected to have a significant impact on reaching the high sustainable modal share ambitions of the city of Turku.

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